

ISic0509

I.Sicily inscription 0509

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.11.12 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo Civico di
Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 120 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth 54 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-10: 30-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [Imp(eratori)Caesari]
2. d(omino) n(ostro) F[l(avio)Valentini]
3. ano pio [felici]
4. semper Aug[usto]
5. M(arcus) Valerius
6. Quintianus
7. v(ir) c(larissimus) cons(ularis) p(rovincia) S(iciliae)
8. clementiae
9. pietatique eius
10. semper dicatis
11. simus

Apparatus

Text of Marino 1978

Translation (en)

To the emperor Caesar, our lord Flavius Valentinianus, pious, fortunate, forever

Augustus; Marcus Valerius Quintianus, of clarissimus rank, governor (consularis) of the province of Sicilia, most dedicated to his clemency and piety (set this up) [translation of Gehn and Machado, LSA 2063]

Commentary

Traces of a probably C3 AD inscription are visible between the final lines

Digital identifiers:

TM 491734

EDCS 22000815

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7229 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Marino, R. 1978. Su alcune iscrizioni latine del palazzo municipale di Marsala. *Kokalos*. 24: 77-111. At 106-110 no.4

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